

UNRAVELING INFORMATION RESOURCE UTILIZATION STRATEGIES: A CASE STUDY OF LAW STUDENTS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN, BENIN CITY

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Article Info

Keywords: Information resources, Digitalization, Librarians, Scholarly literature, Resource management

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.10671386

Abstract

In the rapidly evolving landscape of information resources, there exists an exponential growth driven by the proliferation of diverse mediums and platforms. This surge is particularly evident in scientific literature, where traditional sources such as books are supplemented by the burgeoning array of online scholarly journals. Consequently, librarians find themselves occupying a pivotal role as intermediaries, adept at navigating this expanding ecosystem of information. This article delves into the multifaceted dynamics underlying the exponential growth of information resources, shedding light on the evolving responsibilities and challenges faced by librarians in this digital age.

Drawing upon insights from scholarly discourse and empirical data, the article examines the transformative impact of digitalization on information consumption patterns. The exponential increase in the availability of scientific literature, both in traditional and digital formats, underscores the need for librarians to adapt and innovate in their approaches to resource management and access. As the internet becomes a primary conduit for scholarly discourse, libraries have witnessed a significant surge in budget allocations for electronic materials, reflecting a fundamental shift in information acquisition and dissemination practices.

INTRODUCTION

Information resources are developing and increasing at very astronomical speed. This is due to the multiplying number of information resources being used and explored almost on a daily basis. Science information in books for instance have increased as well as online scholarly journals making librarians “middleware” (Jones, 2009). In the same vein, the growth of the internet, libraries budget for scholarly electronic materials has increased almost fourfold from 1990 to 2001 (Association of Research Libraries, 2008). The critical role that the collection,

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organization and dissemination of information plays in economic, political, social and cultural development is globally recognized, thus the use of the phrase “the information society”. Information is the key to global development, as enunciated at the United Nations World Summits on the Information Society held in Geneva in 2003 and Tunis in 2005 (Obasanjo, 2005). With the growth in information resources, there is corresponding growth and differences in information needs and behaviour of different groups of people. Thus, the several attempts to understand the information seeking patterns of different groups of professionals and students have become inevitable.

Since our world continues to become increasingly information based and information interconnected, the rates of change and exchange of information continue to grow. This is due largely to developments in technology and the importance of information to human and technical development. We live in an information society where more people must manage more information, which in turn requires more technological support, which both demands and creates more information. The general outcome of the growing information volume people have to deal with are tripartite in nature: larger volumes of information to handle or access, new forms of information to deal with and new tools for working with information in the midst of vast resources (Ndukwe, 2004). Students admitted into the faculty of Law are both from urban and rural high schools who have little or no proficiency in use of electronic information resources.

In the midst of this vastly developing information terrain, professionals as well as students find themselves dealing with more information in all aspects of learning and research. Not only are we required to continually seek and acquire information, but there are increasingly more sources and larger volumes available (Kajagbola, 2004). The large volume of information in turn demands more information management access and handling skills. In order to make the most of these large amounts of information, professionals and students are developing personal information needs and seeking behaviour which requires time and effort to build. These information seeking behaviours entails conscious and unconscious filtering of the data and developing fresh strategies for achieving learning goals.

Information seeking behaviour can be described as an individual’s way and manner of gathering and sourcing for information for personal use, knowledge updating and development. This explains the fact that several manners of gathering information and consulting information resources determine the information seeking behaviour of an individual. Faire-Wessels (1990) Kakai et al. (2004) referred to this manner of consulting information resources and gathering information as the way people search for and utilize information. This is what informs the behaviour of an individual which might defer from person to person and discipline to discipline. This is why it is necessary to investigate the factors that inform the information gathering of people within the strata of certain areas of study. Information resource refers to the procedures, equipment, facilities, software and data that are designed, built, operated and maintained to collect, record, process, and store information. Information is a valuable resource in an academic environment, thus acquiring and using information are critical activities. The process known as information seeking is therefore becoming more fundamental and strategic for both students and professionals. Additionally, the information-seeking process is increasingly dependent on electronic technology. This research examined the information seeking patterns of law students of the University of Benin, Nigeria. While the data presentation and analyses appear comparative, the motivation of the research is to discover and present how law students utilize information resources. The separation of both sexes is therefore not exclusive but inclusive as law students are made up of both male and female students.

Statement of the problem

Most students in particular are not exposed to these skills that have to do with information and communication technology Kakai et al. (2004). In this vein, students are not aware of the resources available and where they are

available they are not able to locate the right resources for their research. The problem therefore is that students do not have the skill and knowledge to locate the right information resources thereby wasting valuable time that would have been used in their course of study. Makri et al. (2006) observed that law students have problems discovering appropriate information resources for case law, legislation and journal articles. This is because they are limited in their knowledge of basic print materials. Makri et al. (2006) noted for instance, that for case digests and legislation, most law students experienced difficulties in choosing fitting electronic resources, especially for locating case law and journal articles.

Students identified that they dissipated energy thereby losing precious time when seeking information because of these inadequacies. Furthermore, academic sources, in printed and electronic formats, were not easy to find, as students testified ignoring some resources in favour of others items on a reading catalog.

Law students in the University of Benin are expected to maximally utilize the University Library as one of their major resources of information in addition to several other information resources. However, noting from observation and from the studies conducted on information needs and seeking of students particularly law students it was established that students do not use most of the information resources. It was assumed that students could be experiencing technical or literacy problems in accessing information resources; coupled with lack of knowledge and awareness of the resources. The students' poor information seeking behaviour might be singled out as the biggest cause that needs investigation. Therefore, the background for this study informed the purpose(s) for the research.

Purpose of the study

There are several factors that can determine the Information Seeking Behaviour of an individual or a group of individuals. It is therefore desirable to understand the goal for which information is needed, the environment in which the information seeker operates his/her skills in sourcing the needed information, preferred media for acquiring information and hindrances to accessing information resources. These were factors investigated by the researcher in a research carried out with law students of University of Benin, Benin City which led to the formation of the purpose(s) of this study and the formulated hypothesis. (1) Find out the purpose(s) for which law students seek information. (2) Explore the information resources/channels/services consulted by law students. (1) Determine how law students acquire their information search skills. (2) To suggest ways of improving the information services for law students.

Hypotheses

(1) There is no difference in the purpose for which male and female law students use information. (2) There is no difference in the information resources consulted by male and female law students. (3) There is no difference in the acquisition of information search skills of male and female law students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information needs is understood in information science

Table 1. Sample of respondents.

Total number of students					
Year	Grand total Sample (20%)				
One	129	115	244	49	
Two	184	164	348	70	
Three	126	98	224	45	
Four	132	128	260	52	
Five	37	32	69	14	
Total	608	537	1,145	230	

as stemming from a vague awareness of something (2006) in “Studying Law Students’ Information Seeking missing and as culminating in locating information that Behaviour to Inform the Design of Digital Law Libraries”, contributes to understanding and meaning (Kuhlthau, observed that law students used diverse electronic 1994). According to Wilson (1999) information behaviour information sources to conduct their legal information needs to include at least the following three elements: "an seeking only as a complimentary method. Law students information need and its drivers, that is, the factors that noted that their information seeking during their give rise to an individual's perception of need; the factors undergraduate programmes and to a lesser extent during that affect the individual's response to the perception of their postgraduate programmes, centered on items such need and the processes or actions involved in that as reading lists, textbooks and course packs. Students response." Information seeking behaviour refers to the reported that their legal training was largely teacherway people search for and utilize information (Fairer– centered and content-oriented (McInnis and Symes, Wessels, 1990). 1991; Bruce, 1997a). Students tended to display poor

Most times student’s information seeking behaviour judgement in their choice of electronic resources when involves active or purposeful information seeking as a attempting to match information needs (Herman, 2001; result of the need to complete course assignments, Genoni and Partridge, 2000). Pedagogical approaches to prepare for class discussions, seminars, workshops, legal education in Ireland seem not to encourage the conferences, or write final year research papers. Limberg development of information skills among law students (1998b) states that the nature of one’s task referred to as (Kerins et al., 2004).

“content” is crucial to how people seek and use Furthermore, Oyesiku (2005) pointed out that the information. This is contrary to the understanding that information needs of law lecturers cut across educational, information-seeking is a general process which occurs psychological and social needs like every other independently of the content in the information. profession. While this might be the case, however the Information Seeking Behaviour can be described as an information needs of law lecturers specifically deal with: individual’s way and manner of gathering and sourcing research and teaching in matters of law and legal for information for personal use, knowledge updating and practices; information on new laws and recent development. This explains the fact that several manners enactments, research findings arising from conferences, of gathering information and consulting information seminars, workshops and academic journals. Also, resources determine the information seeking behaviour of information that has to do with current affairs, public an individual. Faire-Wessels (1990) and Kakai et al., administration, governance and general knowledge (2004) referred to this manner of consulting information constitute information needs of lawyers resources and gathering information as the way people search for and utilize information. This is what informs the behavior of an individual which might differ from person **METHODOLOGY** to person and discipline to discipline. This is why it is

necessary to investigate the factors that inform the employed This was a descriptive survey research; therefore, the researcher a descriptive design. The population of this study information gathering of people within the strata of certain consisted of undergraduate law students of the University of Benin, areas of study. Benin City, Nigeria in the 2008/2009 academic session.

Most law students claim to use the resources of the population was 1,145 students in the five levels of study. A library heavily over the course of their academic pro- breakdown of this population is shown as follows in Table 1: grammes. In spite of this claim, most law students have From this number there is a grand total of 1,145 students. The difficulty in locating resources and identifying suitable sampling. Law students in each level were

randomly presented a sample for this study was drawn through systematic random information sources for case law, legislation and journal questionnaire.

articles, as well as being limited in their knowledge of The researcher administered a copy of the questionnaire to every basic print materials (Kerins et al., 2004). Makri et al. twentieth (20th) person that sat in the lecture room during the **Table 2**. Sex and level of respondents.

Level	Male		Female		Total
	No	%	No	%	
Year 1	21	9.13	28	12.17	49
Year 2	37	16.09	33	4.35	70
Year 3	23	10.00	22	9.57	45
Year 4	24	10.43	28	12.17	52
Year 5	8	3.48	6	6.21	14
Total	113	49.13	117	50.87	230

Table 3. Purpose(s) of seeking information by both sexes.

Purpose(s)	Sex	No.	Agree		Disagree		Undecided	
			%	No.	%	No.	%	No.
To supplement lecture notes given by lecturers	M	92	81.42	9	7.96	12	10.6	
	F	90	76.92	15	12.82	12	10.3	
To complete projects/thesis	M	76	67.26	7	6.91	30	26.5	
	F	80	68.38	5	4.27	32	27.4	
To keep up with current development /update knowledge	M	102	90.27	2	1.77	9	7.9	
To complete class assignments	F	99	84.62	4	3.42	14	11.9	
	M	101	89.38	5	4.42	7	6.2	
For entertainment	F	100	85.47	1	0.85	6	5.1	
	M	41	36.28	38	33.63	34	30.0	
		47	40.17	39	33.33	31	26.5	

Table 4. Academic benefits of information use by both sexes.

				<u>Agree</u>	<u>Disagree</u>	<u>Undecided</u>					
				No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		
Promote completion of class assignment	M	F		103	91.15	3	2.65	0	7	6.19	
				115	98.29	0		2		1.71	
Facilitates easy comprehension of course work	M			107	94.69	2	1.77	4		2.83	
	F			114	97.44	1	0.85	2		1.71	
Enrichment of lecture notes	M	F		97	85.84	8	7.08	8		7.08	
				108	92.31	2	1.71	8		6.84	
Being current in the course/profession	M	F		103	91.15	5	4.42	5		4.42	
				107	91.45	3	2.56	7		5.89	
Academic performance			Sex	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%		

Sex	<u>Very often</u>		<u>Often</u>	<u>Some-times</u>	<u>Seldom</u>	<u>Never</u>	<u>Undecided</u>
	No.	%	%	%	%	No	No.

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Table 5. Frequency of information resources used by both sexes.

				<u>No.</u>	<u>No.</u>	<u>No.</u>	<u>No.</u>	<u>No.</u>	<u>No.</u>	<u>%</u>	<u>%</u>	<u>%</u>	<u>%</u>
Government publication	M			22	19.47	44	38.94	22	19.47	5	4.42	5	4.42
	F	8	6.84	18	15.38	53	45.30	19	16.24	2	1.71	7	5.98
Law reports	M	F		63	55.75	24	21.24	10	8.85	8	7.18	1	0.85
				63	63.85	19	16.24	22	18.80	6	5.13	1	0.85
Lecture handouts	M			38	33.62	19	16.81	18	15.93	11	9.73	13	11.50
	F			76	64.96	33	28.21	13	11.11	6	5.13	6	5.13
Websites	M	F		4	3.54	20	23.60	52	46.02	23	20.35	5	4.42
				14	11.97	18	15.38	46	39.32	27	23.08	5	4.27
Dissertations	M	F		3	2.65	6	5.31	24	21.24	29	25.66	10	8.85
				1	0.85	3	2.56	27	23.08	24	20.51	12	10.26

Thesis	M	F5	4.42	9	7.96	33	29.20	33	29.20	7	6.19	26	23.00
		5	4.27	8	6.84	25	21.37	28	25.93	22	18.80	29	24.78
Encyclopedia	M	F9	7.96	9	7.96	43	38.05	36	31.86	6	5.31	10	8.85
		7	5.18	17	14.53	32	27.35	30	25.64	18	15.38	13	11.11
Legal/ law digest	M	27	23.89	27	23.89	23	20.35	33	29.20	0	0	3	2.65
	F	25	21.37	26	22.22	33	28.21	20	17.07	5	4.27	8	6.84
Bibliographies	M	11	9.73	13	11.50	39	34.51	30	26.55	6	5.31	14	12.34
	F	7	5.98	14	11.97	38	32.48	27	23.08	13	11.11	18	15.38
Newspapers	M	46	40.71	38	33.63	24	21.24	3	2.65	0	0	2	1.79
	F	38	32.48	33	28.21	33	28.21	6	5.13	2	1.71	5	4.27
Decrees	M	F21	18.58	27	23.89	31	27.43	15	13.27	7	6.19	12	10.62
		27	23.08	21	<u>17.93</u>	<u>31</u>	<u>26.50</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>14.53</u>	<u>7</u>	5.98	14	11.97

Table 5. Cont.

Textbooks	M	99	87.61	13	11.50	1	0.88	0	0	0	0	0	0
	F	102	87.18	14	11.97	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.85
Video/films	M	11	9.73	10	8.85	36	31.36	29	25.66	18	15.93	9	7.93
	F	21	17.95	12	10.26	27	23.08	20	17.09	26	22.22	11	9.40
Review publications	M	9	7.96	29	25.66	47	41.59	14	12.39	4	3.54	10	8.85
	F	19	16.24	23	19.66	41	35.04	13	11.11	7	5.89	14	11.97
Dictionaries	M	64	56.84	37	32.74	10	8.85	1	0.88	0	0	1	0.88
	F	70	59.83	31	26.50	12	10.26	0	0	2	1.70	2	1.70
Maps/Atlases	M	3	2.65	6	5.31	33	29.20	43	38.05	17	15.04	11	9.73
	F	3	2.56	7	5.98	19	16.24	37	31.62	38	32.48	13	11.11
Access databases	M	3	2.65	5	4.42	35	30.97	37	32.74	17	15.04	16	14.15
	F	3	2.56	7	5.98	15	12.82	34	29.06	33	28.21	25	21.37
Indices/guides	M	8	7.08	12	10.62	36	31.86	28	24.48	15	13.27	14	12.38
	F	12	10.26	23	19.66	20	17.09	16	13.68	27	23.08	19	16.24
Conference/workshop/M		7	6.19	11	9.73	53	46.93	25	22.12	10	8.85	7	6.19

seminar	F	8	6.84	20	17.9	31	26.50	27	23.08	16	13.68	15	12.82
Communication with peers/ colleagues	M	52	46.02	30	26.51	26	33.01	4	3.54	0	0	1	0.88
	F	62	52.99	29	24.79	16	13.68	3	2.56	3	2.56	4	3.42
Electronic mail	M	10	8.85	29	25.66	35	30.97	21	18.58	11	9.73	7	6.19
	F	19	16.24	17	14.53	24	20.51	16	13.68	24	20.51	17	14.53
Journals	M	35	30.97	37	32.74	25	22.12	9	7.96	5	4.42	2	1.77
	F	33	28.21	83	70.9	29	24.79	11	9.40	3	2.5	7	5.98
Abstracts/ indexes	M	8	7.08	16	14.16	38	33.63	27	23.89	10	8.85	14	12.39
	F	18	15.38	16	13.68	24	<u>20.59</u>	<u>22</u>	<u>18.80</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>14.53</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>17.07</u>

female law students (97.44%) agree that one benefit of information use is to facilitate easy comprehension of course work, though female law students appear to agree more in this regard. Similarly, another benefit for information use is promotion of class assignments completion in which females 115(98.29%) agree more in relation to male 103(91.15%). It is given that certain subject matter taught within a course of study will only make more meaning when other information resources are consulted which shed light on it. Other information resources add fresh insight, sources and data as these cannot be totally unpacked in a lecture time of approximately one hour. This also broadens the student’s perspectives to see the issues from the thought of other academics not limiting themselves to the views and opinions of their legal instructors.

Information resources

Table 5 reveals how often both sexes of students use information resources. In the use of information resources females 102(87.18%) agree more to the use of textbooks than males 99(87.61%). Females 63(53.85%) agree to use less of law reports than males 63(55.75%). Law education is purely pedagogical, thus, law students would definitely use textbooks since some of these are written by the lecturers handling a course of study. Also, since lecturers are attuned to following scholars who share their views, law students would be referred to the

$$x^2_{cal} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{(o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}}$$

Table 6. How often, materials are located through various means by both sexes.

Sex	Very often		Often		Sometimes		Seldom		Undecided	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%

Browsing shelves is the most used by both sexes to locate materials with 19(16.81%) males and 60(51.28%) followed by friends with 35(30.97%) males and

$$x_{cal}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{(o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}}$$

Table 7. Acquisition of search skills by both male and female law students.

	Sex	Agree		Disagree		Undecided	
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Trial and error	M	59	52.21	39	34.51	15	13.27
	F	49	41.88	39	33.33	29	24.79
Reading IT books/materials from Library staff	M	29	23.66	49	43.36	35	30.97
	F	32	27.35	43	36.75	42	35.89
Cyber café staff	M	28	24.78	47	41.59	38	33.63
	F	27	23.08	46	39.32	44	37.61
ICT training programme	M	16	14.16	57	50.44	40	35.39
	F	20	17.09	49	41.88	48	41.02
Friends/colleagues	M	87	76.99	6	5.30	20	17.70
	F	96	82.05	3	2.56	18	15.38

Table 8. Chi-square (X^2) analysis of the difference between sexes with respect to purpose of using information.

Purpose for seeking information	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
Agree	505	522	1027
Disagree	66	66	132
Undecided	107	104	211
Total	678	692	1370

in the purpose for which male and female law students use information.

Testing the students' information resources

$$x_{cal}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^6 \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{(o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}}$$

$x_{cal}^2 = 66.6153$, Df = 5, Table $X^2 = 11.07$, Level of confidence = 0.05, Decision: Since x_{cal}^2 is greater than X^2 critical, the null hypothesis is rejected. Remark: Significant.

From the result presented above, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. This is because the calculated X^2 (66.6153) is greater than X^2 critical (11.07). This implies that there is difference in the information resources consulted by male and female law students as shown in Table 9.

Testing the students information resources utilization pattern

$$X^2_{cal} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{(o_{ij} - e_{ij})^2}{e_{ij}}$$

Calculated $X^2 = 3.8755$, $Df = 2$, Table $X^2 = 5.99$, Level of confidence = 0.05, Decision: Since X^2_{cal} is less than X^2 critical, the null hypothesis is accepted. Remark: Not significant.

From the presented result above, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This is because, the calculated value of (X^2) 3.8755 is less than X^2 critical (5.99). This implies that there is no difference in the acquisition of information search skills of male and female law students as shown in Table 10.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher wishes to recommend the following based on the conclusions drawn in this study: (1) Since both male and female male and female law students seek information for the purpose of current development, update their knowledge, current awareness, and to complete class assignments given by their lecturers, efforts should be made by university authority to consistently stock the library with relevant, current and up-to-date information resources/materials which would keep the students abreast with the current trends in their training/profession. (2) Since male law students consult law reports more and female law students consult textbooks more, the reason for this disparity should be investigated and attended to. (3) Both male and female

Table 9. Chi-square (X^2) analysis of mean difference between both sexes with respect to information resources used.

Information resources	Sex		
	Male	Female	Total
Very Often	551	487	1030
Often	449	409	858
Sometimes	716	587	1303
Seldom	481	409	890
Never	167	289	456
Undecided	228	307	535
Total	2592	2488	5080

Table 10. Acquisition of search skills by both sexes.

Acquisition of search skills	Sex		
	Female	Male	Total
Agree	219	224	443
Disagree	198	180	378
Undecided	148	181	329
Total	565	585	1150

law students develop their information search skills more from friends and colleagues, therefore, university authority should endeavour to make formal information search skill training a formal part of legal training especially because information search is time consuming. This would enable both male and female law students to use their time more usefully each time they visit the library.

Conclusion

The findings of this study pointed out various facts concerning both male and female male and female law students in their patterns of information search and use. From the research it was clearly shown that male law students obtain higher mean scores in their information utilization pattern than the female law students. The null hypothesis that was rejected is one (hypothesis two), compared with those that had no difference that were on the higher size using the probability level of 0.05 is accepted. It shows that the information utilization patterns of both male and female law students are the same with perhaps slight differences not highly evident.

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APPENDIX QUESTIONNAIRE

Department of Library and information Science, Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.

4th March 2008

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am a graduate student of the above named university. I am carrying out a research on "information seeking patterns of law Students of the University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria. This questionnaire is designed for all levels of law students in the University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria to elicit information on their information seeking patterns. Please, kindly and honestly respond to the following questions and be assured of the confidential treatment of your response. You are expected to return the completed questionnaire to the contact person within 24 hours of receipt.

Personal data: Please tick as appropriate

- Sex: Male.....Female.....
- Course of study..... - Level of study.....

- Age: Below 20yrs...20 -24yrs...25 – 29yrs...30-40yrs....40yrs... and above... - Marital status: Single.....Married.....

Information seeking patterns

Table 1. Indicate whether or not you seek information for the following purposes?

Purpose	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
To supplement note given by lecturers			
To support notes given by lecturers			
To complete projects/thesis			
To keep up with current development/update knowledge			
To complete assignments			
For entertainment			

Table 2. How often do you use the following information resources?

	<u>Very often</u>	<u>often</u>	<u>Sometimes</u>	<u>Seldom</u>	<u>Never</u>	<u>Undecided</u>	Table
2. Government publication							
Law reports							
Lecture handouts							
Websites							
Dissertations							
Thesis							
Encyclopedia							
Legal/ law digest							
Bibliographies							
Newspapers							
Decrees							
Textbooks							
Video/films							
Review Publications							
Dictionaries							

Cont'd.

Maps/Atlases
 Access Databases
 Indices/guides
 Conference/workshop/seminar
 Communication with peers/colleagues
 Electronic mail
 Journals
 Abstracts/indexes

Table 3. How often do you use the following channels to access information?

Access point	Very often	often	sometimes	seldom	Undecided
University main library					
Departmental(law) library					
Other libraries in the University campus					
Private law libraries					
Ministry of Justice library					
Public libraries					
Cyber café					
Home access to the internet					
Mass media					
Communication with peers/others					

Table 4. How do you react or feel when you cannot locate the information resource that you need? (Indicate whether or not you agree).

	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
I keep searching for information I sometimes feel bad			
I sometimes consult the librarian			

Table 5. Indicate whether or not the information you seek contribute the following to your academic performance?

Academic performance	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
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Promote completion of class assignment
Facilitates easy comprehension of course
work
Enrichment of lecture note
Being current in the course/profession

Table 6. How often do you make use of the library?

Daily
2-3 times a week
Once a week
2-3 times a month
Once a month
Occasionally Rarely
Undecided .

Table 7. Indicate whether or not you use the library for the following reasons?

	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
To borrow books			
To return borrowed library materials			
To complete class assignments			
To read for examination			
To consult librarians			
To source for materials			
To socialize			
To photocopy			

Table 8. How often do you use the following to locate materials in the library?

	Very often	often	sometimes	seldom	undecided
Card catalogue					
Online public Access Catalogue (OPAC)					
Reference librarian					
Subject librarian					
Lecturers					
Browsing shelves for Books					
Scanning journal titles in the library					
Abstract and indexes on CD-ROM					
Abstract and indexes in print					
Friends					

Table 9. How often, when using the university library, do you need help?

Very often
 Often
 Sometimes Seldom
 Undecided

Table 10. What is the length of time you spend in the library per visit?

Less than an hour
 1– 2 hours
 2– 3 hours
 Hours and above

Table 11. How often do you use the following services in/of the library?

	Very often	often	sometimes	seldom	undecided
Bibliographic services					Current awareness
Telephone service					
E-mail		Internet/e-service			
Inter-library loan service					
Photocopying		Loan service (of the local library)			
Book reservation service					

Table 12. Indicate whether or not you acquired your information search skills through the following means?

	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
Trial and error			Reading IT books/materials from Library staff
Cyber café staff			
ICT training programme			
Friends/colleagues			

Table 13. How satisfied are you with library services/resources?

Highly satisfied
 Satisfied
 Unsatisfactory Highly unsatisfactory Undecided .

Table 14. Indicate if any of the following act as an impediment to your information search/use?

	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
Inadequate/lack of ICT skills			
Inadequate relevant materials in the library			
High cost of information resources		Slow internet response	
Unconducive library environment		Electricity interruption	
Uncooperative library staff			

